

THE IMPACT OF INCOME ON THE CHOICE OF COOKING ENERGY AMONG HOUSEHOLDS IN MTENDERE, LUSAKA, ZAMBIA

MUKANEMA M.*, CHIGUVI D.**

*School of Engineering, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Zambia, Lusaka, Zambia

**Faculty of Commerce, Department of Entrepreneurship, BA ISAGO University, Gaborone, Botswana

maonamukanema@gmail.com

dchiguvi@gmail.com

Abstract-This study investigates how household income influences the choice of cooking energy in Mtendere, a high-density area in Lusaka, Zambia. Quantitative research was employed and data was collected through the use of questionnaires. The results reveal that 47.8% of households earn between ZMW 1,001 and 3,000 per month, with 50.4% spending ZMW 101–300 on cooking energy. A multinomial logit regression analysis established that higher income and education levels are strong predictors of cleaner fuel adoption, such as electricity and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG). In contrast, households with lower incomes tend to rely on traditional fuels like firewood and charcoal, influenced partly by cultural norms. Alarming, 62.5% of respondents underestimated the health risks associated with charcoal use, and 64.1% were unaware of its environmental impact, including deforestation and carbon emissions. The findings underscore the urgent need for targeted policy interventions to promote energy transition and public awareness in low-income communities.

Keywords: Household Energy Choices, Socio-Economic Determinants, Cooking Energy, Multinomial Logit Analysis, Cultural Dynamics

1. INTRODUCTION

The energy demand and consumption in Sub-Saharan Africa has been on a steady rise and is expected to continue growing as most African economies continue to pursue economic development. According to a report by IEA (2023) almost 80–90% of households in developing countries, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa, lack sufficient, reliable, and affordable cooking energy. The energy landscape in Africa, particularly in relation to cooking fuels, is characterized by a heavy reliance on traditional biomass, such as firewood and charcoal. This reliance poses significant health, environmental, and economic challenges. Approximately 1 billion people in sub-Saharan Africa still rely on traditional biomass for

cooking (Philibert, 2022). WHO (2021) reported that smoke from these cooking fuels leads to adverse health effects from indoor air pollution, which is responsible for an estimated 500,000 premature deaths annually across the continent. The overdependence on biomass also contributes to deforestation and environmental degradation, exacerbating climate change and compromising the sustainability of local ecosystems (Arnold, et al., 2006).

Zambia is a landlocked, resource-rich, lower-middle-income country with sparsely populated land in the heart of Southern Africa and covers 752,614 square kilometers. The report by Zambia Statistics Agency (2022) stated that forest and woodlands cover around 45 million hectares, or over 60% of Zambia’s total land area. In Zambia, the energy situation mirrors broader regional trends, with over 90.6% of households relying on firewood and charcoal as their primary cooking fuels. Zambia’s sources of energy include; electricity, petroleum, coal, biomass, and renewable energy. The major source of energy in Zambia is wood fuel (i.e. firewood and charcoal), with the largest consumer group being households in both rural and urban areas. As of 2022 wood fuel accounted for about 70 percent of the total national energy consumption in the country in form of firewood and charcoal while electricity, petroleum and coal account for 14 percent, 12 percent and 2 percent respectively as shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Zambia’s Energy Mix
Source: (Ministry of Energy, 2020)

Cooking fuels in Zambia are a critical component of household energy consumption, particularly as the majority of the population relies on traditional methods that have implications for health, environment, and socio-economic development. In Zambia, wood fuel is the principal source of energy. The combination of health, socio-economic, and environmental consequences of biomass use for household energy, suggest the urgent need to identify strategies to promote the more efficient use of biomass resources and the adoption of more sustainable, cleaner fuel sources (Miah, et al., 2011; Lewis & Pattanayak, 2012). The challenge of unsustainable biomass utilization to meet household energy requirements is particularly acute in Zambia. According to the Living Conditions Monitoring Survey conducted by Zambia Statistics Agency (2022), 51.4% of all Zambian households use firewood as the main source of cooking energy, 39.2% use charcoal and only 8.5% use electricity. However, there is a distinct difference between the urban and rural households. In rural areas, 81.9% of the households used firewood for cooking, followed by charcoal with 15.8%; and electricity is used by only 1.2%. In contrast, most households in urban areas use charcoal for cooking 73%, followed by electricity 19.1% while only a small proportion use firewood 7.5% as shown in figure 1.

Fig. 2. Percentage Distribution of Households by Main Source of Energy for Cooking in Rural and Urban, Zambia, 2015 and 2022
 Source: (Zambia Statistics Agency, 2022)

Mtendere, a densely populated urban area in Lusaka, Zambia, has seen a gradual evolution in household cooking technologies. Historically, like much of Zambia, households in Mtendere predominantly rely on traditional biomass fuels such as firewood and charcoal for cooking (Wang, et al., 2022). Traditional biomass cooking involved the use of inefficient three-stone stoves fed by fuelwood, charcoal, dung, agricultural waste, and other waste products (Bailis, et al., 2015). The reliance on biomass fuels is usually due to the accessibility and low upfront cost of these fuels, despite their inefficiency and the environmental and health hazards associated with them (Makonese, et al., 2017). In the 1990s and early 2000s, the urbanization of areas like Mtendere led to increased demand for charcoal, which became the dominant cooking fuel. This period marked significant deforestation rates as rural-urban migration surged and the demand for charcoal grew (Kaimowitz & Angelsen, 1998). The widespread use of these fuels is largely driven by economic constraints, lack of awareness of their adverse effects, limited access to modern energy sources,

and cultural preferences (Kizilcec, et al., 2022; Bonjour, et al., 2013). Urban areas have seen a rise in charcoal use due to population growth and the affordability issues associated with cleaner alternatives like liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) and electricity (Mulenga, et al., 2019). Despite the introduction of alternatives like kerosene stoves and, later, electric cookers, the high cost of appliances and the unreliability of electricity supply hindered their adoption among low-income households (Kizilcec, et al., 2022).

Recognizing the adverse impacts of these traditional fuels on health, the environment, and socio-economic development, the Zambian government, along with international partners, has undertaken initiatives to promote clean cooking solutions. Efforts to promote clean cooking in Zambia began in the late 1990s and early 2000s, with various non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and international development agencies introducing improved cook stoves (ICS) and cleaner fuels on a small scale. The report by The World Bank, (2011) mentioned that these early initiatives were often fragmented, with limited coordination and sustainability, focusing mainly on the distribution of improved biomass stoves that were designed to be more efficient and reduce emissions compared to traditional cooking methods. In 2006, Zambia became part of the United Nations Sustainable Energy for All (SEforALL) initiative, which aimed to ensure universal access to modern energy services, including clean cooking solutions, by 2030. The report Sustainable Energy for All (2012) mentioned that this initiative spurred the government to take a more active role in coordinating clean cooking efforts, recognizing the need for a strategic approach to scale up adoption.

The formal development of Zambia’s National Clean Cooking Strategy gained momentum in the mid-2010s, as awareness of the need for coordinated action grew. In 2015, the Zambian government, through the Ministry of Energy, began drafting the National Energy Policy with a clear emphasis on clean cooking technologies. According to report, Ministry of Energy (2019) this policy aimed to address the challenges of energy access and sustainability by promoting alternative energy sources, including electricity, liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), and improved biomass stoves. In 2019, the National Energy Policy was officially launched, providing a comprehensive framework for the country’s energy sector, including specific targets for clean cooking. The policy set ambitious goals, such as increasing the share of households using clean cooking solutions to 40% by 2030. The report, Ministry of Energy (2019) asserted that this marked a significant shift from ad hoc efforts to a more structured and strategic approach. The Zambian government, through policies like the National Energy Policy (NEP) of 2019 and initiatives under the Ministry of Energy, has aimed to promote sustainable energy solutions, including cleaner cooking technologies. The report, Ministry of Energy (2019) mentioned that the government’s role includes setting regulatory frameworks, providing subsidies, and facilitating access to financing for modern energy solutions. Additionally, the report Rural Electrification Authority (2021) mentioned that efforts are underway to improve access to electricity,

which indirectly supports the adoption of electric cooking solutions.

Several NGOs and international organizations, such as the Global Alliance for Clean Cook stoves, USAID Alternative to charcoal Project and SNV Netherlands Development Organization, have been actively involved in promoting clean cooking solutions in Zambia, including Mtendere. These organizations often focus on awareness campaigns, pilot projects, and providing financial support or subsidies for cleaner cook stove adoption. According to SNV Netherlands Development Organisation, (2018) SNV's 'Sustainable Energy for All' initiative promotes the adoption of improved cook stoves and solar cookers by working closely with local communities and stakeholders. A multi-faceted approach, incorporating financial incentives, community engagement, and enhanced supply chains, is essential for scaling up the adoption of clean cooking technologies in Zambia and the wider African region (MCFA, 2024)

The future outlook for cooking technologies in Mtendere is shaped by a blend of socio-economic factors, government policies, and global trends towards sustainability. The report, IEA (2022) asserted that as Government continues to push for renewable energy adoption, there is potential for increased uptake of electric and LPG stoves, especially if electricity supply becomes more stable and affordable. Furthermore, with ongoing efforts by NGOs and the private sector to innovate and subsidize the cost of clean cook stoves, there is hope for broader adoption. The introduction of pay-as-you-go (PAYG) models for LPG and electricity could further ease the financial burden on households, making cleaner options more accessible (Sharma & Sinkko, 2022). Technological advancements and increased awareness about the health impacts of traditional cooking methods are likely to drive change. However, significant challenges remain, including overcoming cultural preferences and ensuring that clean cooking technologies are not only affordable but also accessible to the most vulnerable populations (IRENA, 2024; Zhang, 2022).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents the literature review of the study on the impact of income on the choice of cooking energy among household.

Types of cooking energy

Different terminologies and definitions are used in categorizing household cooking energy types as shown in Figure 3. Depending on typical level of energy development, type of fuels used for cooking in households can be categorized as traditional, intermediate and modern. Based on the way these cooking energy types are produced or extracted, they are sometimes termed as primary and secondary. Likewise, cooking energy types can be categorized as renewables and non-renewables. Furthermore, there are also wide variations in the level of consumption and the patterns cooking energy use by households based on their levels of urbanization and income. These categorizations, in general, include rural and urban households, and low income and high income households. Besides, use of fuels for household

cooking is also concentrated in certain countries, e.g., coal in China, charcoal in SSA, dung in India, kerosene in Djibouti and electricity in South Africa (Smith, et al., 2012).

2.1. Traditional Fuels

Traditional fuels include biomass such as firewood, charcoal, crop residues, and animal dung. These are widely used in low-income rural areas due to their low cost and accessibility. Traditional fuels are commonly harvested from local environments and are usually considered unsustainable due to their environmental impact. They release significant levels of pollutants, contributing to indoor air pollution and respiratory issues, especially among women and children who are often the primary users (Smith, 2000). Studies show that reliance on traditional fuels is associated with several socio-economic and environmental problems. Heltberg (2005) found that lower-income households in rural Guatemala primarily relied on firewood due to the lack of affordable alternatives. Similarly, Bruce, et al (2000) demonstrated the adverse health effects of biomass fuels, including respiratory infections, which are prevalent in households where traditional fuels dominate.

2.2. Intermediate or transitional fuels

Intermediate or transitional fuels are energy sources that represent a middle step between traditional biomass fuels and cleaner, modern fuels. These intermediate fuels, including wood pellets, charcoal, briquettes, lignite, coal and kerosene, offer a compromise in terms of cost, accessibility, and pollution levels. Kerosene, a liquid fossil fuel, is particularly popular in urban and peri-urban areas where access to firewood is limited, and alternative clean fuels are unaffordable. Coal is another transitional fuel used in specific regions, especially where it is readily available and affordable. However, both kerosene and coal have health risks, emitting pollutants harmful to human health and contributing to air pollution (Hanna, et al., 2016). These fuels tend to serve as stepping stones in the energy ladder for households that are starting to move away from biomass but cannot yet afford cleaner, modern alternatives. A study by Miller & Mobarak (2013) found that households in Bangladesh considered kerosene as an intermediate option due to its affordability and accessibility, despite awareness of its health risks. These transitional fuels, though less polluting than biomass, still contribute to both household and environmental health hazards.

2.3. Modern Fuels

Modern fuels include liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), electricity, solar, biogas, natural gas, gelfuel, plant oils and dimethyl ether. These fuels are considered cleaner as they produce minimal indoor pollutants and are more efficient in energy conversion. LPG and electricity are prominent choices for urban households in developing countries and have been widely promoted by governments and non-governmental organizations due to their health benefits (Barnes, et al., 2005). Electricity, typically used

through induction or electric stoves, offers a high-efficiency, low-pollution cooking solution, although access remains limited in low-income areas due to cost and infrastructure issues. In many sub-Saharan African countries, despite increasing urbanization, electricity is unaffordable for the majority, which limits its adoption (World Bank, 2025). In 2024, Zambia experienced a significant rise in the use of liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) for household cooking, marked by a substantial 31.6% increase in LPG consumption (ERB, 2024). Studies indicate that access to modern fuels significantly improves indoor air quality and reduces health risks associated with traditional fuels. For instance, Mortimer, et al. (2017) observed a notable improvement in respiratory health in Malawian households that transitioned from wood to LPG. Moreover, Asante, et al. (2018) highlighted the role of income levels in determining access to LPG, emphasizing that although LPG is cleaner, its higher cost compared to biomass remains a barrier for many low-income households.

2.4. Primary

Primary cooking energy sources are typically traditional, readily accessible, and low-cost fuels, though they often have high environmental and health impacts. Primary energy is directly obtained from biomass fuels such as fuelwood, agricultural waste, animal dung, coal. Biomass fuels particularly firewood and charcoal, remain dominant in rural and low-income households, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia (IEA, 2017). Households often rely on biomass because it is locally available and affordable, despite the severe health risks from indoor air pollution and environmental degradation associated with deforestation (Bruce, et al., 2015; WHO, 2021). In many rural areas, households collect agricultural residues or dung for cooking, a practice observed in low-income regions where alternatives are either inaccessible or unaffordable (Malla & Timilsina, 2014). Although such sources are affordable, they are inefficient and emit harmful pollutants, impacting respiratory health and leading to high carbon emissions (Smith, et al., 2014). Although technically a fossil fuel, coal is also considered a primary cooking fuel in many developing regions due to its availability and relatively low cost. However, its environmental and health risks are substantial, as it emits significant particulate matter and harmful gases (Pachauri, et al., 2004)

2.5. Secondary

Secondary energy sources are generally cleaner, more efficient, and costlier than primary sources. They represent progress toward modern energy. Secondary energy types, which come from transformation of primary energy types, include petroleum products (kerosene, LPG, dimethyl ether) from crude oil, ethanol from sugar cane, charcoal and wood pellets from fuelwood, biogas produced from animal dung and agricultural waste, electricity produced from combustion of fossil-fuels and from renewable energy sources such as solar, hydro and wind. Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) is widely recognized as a cleaner cooking fuel due to its lower

emissions and higher efficiency compared to biomass and coal. Studies show that households that transition to LPG enjoy improved indoor air quality and experience fewer respiratory health issues (Van der Kroon, et al., 2013). LPG adoption is rising in urban areas of developing countries, although high costs and access issues limit its use in rural regions (Bruce, et al., 2015). Electricity as an extremely clean and efficient cooking option, electricity is associated with higher income households and urban areas where infrastructure supports its use (IEA, 2017). In developing regions, electricity is often a secondary choice, available only as grid extension improves and households achieve the economic means to afford it (Miller & Mobarak, 2013). Biogas is increasingly promoted in rural areas as a sustainable, low-emission alternative to traditional biomass fuels, created through anaerobic digestion of organic waste. Studies indicate that biogas adoption significantly reduces indoor air pollution and dependency on firewood, though initial costs and infrastructure requirements can pose barriers (Mwirigi, et al., 2014).

2.6. Renewables

Renewable cooking energy sources are derived from resources that are naturally replenished. These options are increasingly emphasized for their role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable energy access which include biomass, biogas, and solar energy. Biomass (Sustainable) like firewood and agricultural residues when managed sustainably can be considered renewable, as they are regenerated over time. In many rural and low-income areas, sustainable biomass use is common due to its availability, though its use can lead to deforestation and health issues from smoke inhalation when not managed sustainably (IEA, 2017). Modern techniques, like improved cookstoves, can mitigate some of these health and environmental impacts (Bruce, et al., 2015). Biogas, produced from the anaerobic digestion of organic waste, is a renewable energy source gaining traction for its low emissions and efficiency in household cooking (Mwirigi, et al., 2014). Research highlights biogas's potential to reduce reliance on firewood and charcoal, especially in rural areas, as it is both renewable and reduces the need for solid biomass fuels (Cheng, et al., 2014). Solar energy is a clean and renewable cooking source that does not produce any emissions during use. Solar cookers harness direct sunlight for cooking, which is most suitable in regions with ample sunlight. Despite its environmental benefits, solar cooking adoption is limited due to its dependency on sunlight availability, making it impractical for nighttime or cloudy weather use (Otte, 2013).

2.7. Non-renewables

Non-renewable cooking energy sources are derived from finite resources and contribute significantly to environmental degradation and greenhouse gas emissions. Examples include fossil fuels like kerosene, liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), and coal. Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) is a widely used non-renewable fuel for cooking due to its efficiency, cleanliness, and ease of use

compared to biomass. It has become a preferred choice for households transitioning from biomass, but it remains costly and is dependent on the fossil fuel supply chain (Van der Kroon, et al., 2013). Although it produces fewer emissions than solid biomass, it still contributes to carbon emissions (Miller & Mobarak, 2013). Kerosene is commonly used for cooking in some low-income regions where LPG is unaffordable. It is cheaper than LPG but produces high emissions, posing both health and environmental risks. Studies highlight its association with respiratory diseases and its high pollutant levels, making it an unsustainable option (Bruce, et al., 2015). Coal remains a primary cooking fuel in certain areas, especially where it is locally available and affordable. Its use is associated with severe health and environmental hazards due to the release of particulate matter and greenhouse gases. This makes it a significant contributor to household air pollution and deforestation (Pachauri, et al., 2004).

2.8. Rural

In rural areas, traditional biomass sources, including firewood, charcoal, and agricultural residues, are prevalent due to their availability and cost-effectiveness. However, these sources can lead to significant health risks from indoor air pollution, as well as environmental impacts like deforestation. Studies by Bruce, et al., (2015) and Khandker, et al., (2012) highlight that the lack of infrastructure for clean and modern energy in rural areas perpetuates reliance on traditional fuels. Firewood and Agricultural Residues are the primary fuels in rural regions across Sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, and Latin America, primarily due to its accessibility. Women and children are often responsible for gathering firewood, which exposes them to safety risks and limits time for other activities (World Health Organization, 2023). Charcoal is a common cooking fuel in rural and peri-urban areas, especially in regions with limited access to cleaner fuels. Charcoal burns cleaner than raw biomass, making it slightly more efficient for household cooking. However, the process of charcoal production itself is environmentally taxing, leading to deforestation and carbon emissions (Malla & Timilsina, 2014). Despite the predominance of traditional fuels, some rural households are adopting biogas and solar cookers, though the adoption rate remains low due to high upfront costs and inconsistent support infrastructure (Cheng, et al., 2014).

2.9. Urban

In urban areas, access to modern fuels such as liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), electricity, and sometimes natural gas is more common. The demand for cleaner, more efficient cooking fuels is driven by factors such as limited space, a lack of resources like firewood, and greater income levels, which support fuel-switching and modern appliance purchases. However, even in urban areas, disparities exist, with low-income neighborhoods often continuing to rely on a mix of charcoal and kerosene (Pachauri & Spreng, 2011; Van der Kroon, et al., 2013). LPG is the most widely adopted cooking fuel in urban households, valued for its cleanliness, efficiency, and ease of use. Its use is largely influenced by income and policy

incentives; countries with subsidies or price controls on LPG experience higher urban adoption rates, however, affordability remains an issue for lower-income households (Brew-Hammond & Kemausuor, 2009). Electricity is a preferred cooking option in urban areas where infrastructure is reliable and electricity is affordable, although limitations arise in regions with frequent power outages (Rao & Reddy, 2007). Natural gas pipelines are common in larger cities, particularly in higher-income neighborhoods, as it is clean-burning and convenient. Yet, lack of infrastructure in low-income urban areas restricts widespread natural gas adoption (Rao & Reddy, 2007). Despite its drawbacks, kerosene is still used for cooking in some low-income urban households due to its affordability and availability. However, it is associated with high pollutant levels, and its use is increasingly discouraged due to its health impacts (Sovacool, 2012). Urbanization trends tend to drive energy transitions, as cities offer better access to modern fuels and appliances. However, income disparities within urban areas lead to “fuel stacking,” where households use multiple types of cooking fuels depending on cost, availability, and purpose (Heltberg, 2003).

2.10. Low income

In many low-income households, particularly in developing countries, traditional biomass fuels like firewood, charcoal, and agricultural residues dominate due to their availability and affordability. These households often rely on biomass even when aware of its health risks, due to financial constraints and limited access to infrastructure for cleaner fuels (Pachauri & Spreng, 2011). Firewood and Agricultural Residues are primary energy sources for cooking in low-income households in rural areas due to their low cost and availability. In urban areas with limited access to firewood, charcoal is often used as it burns cleaner than raw biomass, producing less smoke. However, charcoal production and use contribute to deforestation and generate high carbon emissions, posing an environmental challenge (Sovacool, 2012). The affordability of charcoal in smaller amounts (despite its high overall price) makes it a common choice in low-income urban households (Van der Kroon, et al., 2013). Some low-income urban households use kerosene for cooking, as it is relatively cheap and widely available. Many countries discourage its use due to the associated health hazards and risks of burns and accidents (Sovacool, 2012). The energy ladder theory suggests that as household incomes increase, they move from solid fuels like biomass to cleaner fuels such as LPG and electricity. However, in reality, many low-income households practice fuel stacking using multiple energy sources based on availability and cost (Masera, et al., 2000).

2.11. High income

High-income households typically have the financial means to afford modern cooking fuels and appliances, leading to a preference for cleaner, more efficient energy sources. These households commonly use fuels such as liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), natural gas, and

electricity, which offer greater convenience and fewer health and environmental risks (Rao & Reddy, 2007). LPG is the most widely used cooking fuel among high-income households due to its efficiency, convenience, and low emissions. It is often subsidized by governments to promote its adoption across income levels, though these subsidies are more accessible to middle- and high-income groups with infrastructure access (Brew-Hammond & Kemausuor, 2009). In many urban high-income households, electricity is used for cooking, especially in countries with reliable power supply. Electric stoves and induction cookers are preferred for their cleanliness, ease of use, and absence of emissions. However, electricity costs and availability often prevent its widespread adoption among low-income households (Kowsari & Zerriffi, 2011). In cities with natural gas infrastructure, high-income households often choose this option as it provides a continuous supply with clean combustion. Its adoption is limited to households in urban areas with sufficient infrastructure, usually those at higher income levels (IEA, 2021). High-income households, with better access to modern fuels and appliances, are more likely to benefit from government policies promoting clean energy. This contrast in energy choices between income groups perpetuates energy inequality, with low-income households bearing higher health and environmental burdens from traditional fuel use (Heltberg, 2005).

Fig.3. Schematic illustration of categorizing household cooking energy types

Source: (Sunil & Timilsina, 2014; IEA, 2012)

House Income

Income is a primary determinant of household cooking technology choices. Income levels are a critical determinant of the type of cooking technology households adopt. Studies have consistently shown that higher income levels are associated with the adoption of cleaner, safer and more efficient cooking technologies. According to Matinga, et al (2013) many low-income households struggle to afford the upfront/or initial cost and ongoing expenses related to cleaner associated with cleaner cooking technologies, even if they are aware of the long-term health and environmental benefits. This was demonstrated in a study conducted in rural Eastern Cape, South Africa, where higher-income households were more likely to adopt gas or electric stoves, while poorer families continued using biomass fuels. Similarly, Zulu & Richardson (2013) examined the relationship between income levels and cooking fuel choices in urban Zambian households. The study found that low-income households

in Lusaka, despite being aware of the benefits of Liquid Petroleum Gas continued to rely on charcoal because of its affordability and availability. Cost remains a significant barrier for lower-income households, which typically revert to biomass fuels. Additionally, Van der Kroon, et al (2013) also conducted a study showing that wealthier households in developing countries tend to transition from biomass fuels to cleaner options as their income rises. The study found that income plays a dual role: enabling the purchase of modern cooking appliances and sustaining the ongoing fuel costs. This transition is often driven by the desire for convenience, time savings, and improved indoor air quality. However, lower-income households frequently rely on cheaper and more accessible traditional biomass fuels, despite the known health and environmental disadvantages (Wu, 2021). The upfront costs of modern stoves and the recurring costs of cleaner fuels often deter lower-income households from making the switch, despite potential long-term savings and health benefits (Toman & Bluffstone, 2017). In the case of Mtendere, the affordability of cleaner cooking technologies is likely a key challenge for widespread adoption.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a cross-sectional design with a multistage cluster sampling technique to randomly select 400 households from urban and peri-rural areas of Mtendere, drawn from a population of 106,128. Data were collected ethically through questionnaires administered across five locations (Mtendere A, B, C, D, and Extension), with 80 respondents from each. The questionnaire was pilot-tested for validity and reliability, and data were cleaned prior to analysis. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS, applying both descriptive (frequencies, modes, means) and inferential statistics (Pearson’s correlation). To assess the factors influencing household choice of cooking technology, the study employed a multinomial logit model (MLM).

4. DATA RESULTS

Table 1. Response rate

Gender of household head	Frequency (Actual responses)	Calculated Sample Size	Response rate (%)
Male	222	400	98.75 %
Female	173		
Total	395		

Source: Raw Data (2025)

The response rate of 98.75%, as shown in Table 1, indicates that the study successfully collected responses from nearly the entire targeted sample size (395 out of 400). This high response rate enhances the reliability and validity of the findings, as it minimizes the potential for non-response bias. This infers that data collection strategy was effective and ensures a robust representation of the target population. Consequently, the results are likely to

provide a comprehensive and accurate insight into household cooking energy choices in Mtendere.

4.2. Demographic Profile

Table 2 provides a summary of demographic information gathered from a sample of 395 respondents. In relation to this study, the table highlights key socio-economic and demographic characteristics of participants, such as gender, age, education level, household size, and income. These variables are critical in understanding the determinants influencing household cooking energy choices in Mtendere.

Table 2. Social-economic characteristics of respondent

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
Gender of Household Head		
Male	222	56.2
Female	173	43.8
Total	395	100
Age (In Years)		
18-24	9	2.3
25-34	68	17.2
35-44	101	25.6
45-54	110	27.8
55-64	64	16.2
65 & above	43	10.9
Total	395	100
Marital Status		
Single	62	15.7
Married	232	58.7
Divorced/Separated	45	11.4
Widowed	56	14.2
Total	395	100
Household Size		
2 persons	33	8.4
3-4 persons	120	30.4
5-6 persons	138	34.9
7-8 persons	73	18.5
More than 9 persons	31	7.8
Total	395	100
Primary Source of Household Income		
Wage only	110	27.8
Wage and Self-employment	44	11.1
Self-employment only	162	41
Unemployed	79	20
Total	395	100
Level of Education		
No formal Education	28	7.1
Primary Education	90	22.8
Secondary Education	175	44.3
Tertiary Education	102	25.8
Total	395	100
Household Monthly Income (K)		
Less than 1,000	87	22
1,001- 3,000	189	47.8
3,001- 6,000	86	21.8
6001- 10,000	20	5.1
More than 10,000	13	3.3
Total	395	100
Monthly Expenditure on Cooking Fuel (K)		
Less than 100	14	3.5
101- 300	199	50.4
301- 600	133	33.7
601- 1,000	39	9.9
More than 1,000	10	2.5
Total	395	100

Source: Raw Data (2025)

4.3. Primary Source of Household Income

Fig.4. Primary Source of Household Income
Source: Raw Data (2025)

The occupational engagement of households reflects a diverse range of activities. It was noted that 27.8% of households rely solely on wage income for their livelihood, 11.1% of households rely on both wage earnings and self-employment. A significant 41% depend exclusively on self-employment, and 20% of household’s report being unemployed as illustrated in Figure 4. The occupational engagement data suggests a diverse economic structure among households. With 41% relying solely on self-employment, this indicates a strong entrepreneurial or informal sector presence, which may reflect adaptability but also economic vulnerability, as such income can be unstable. The 27.8% solely dependent on wages represent a smaller proportion of households with presumably more consistent earnings. The combination of wage earnings and self-employment (11.1%) highlights diversification in income strategies for some households, which could offer resilience against economic shocks. However, the 20% unemployment rate is significant; suggesting a considerable portion of households may face economic hardships and limited access to essential goods and services, potentially influencing their energy and technology adoption choices. A study by Osano, et al., (2020) revealed that the occupational status of the household head positively and significantly influenced the household’s cooking energy choice.

4.4. Monthly Income

The income distribution shows that the majority of households 47.8% fall within the ZMW 1,001–3,000 monthly income range, this is followed by 22% earning less than ZMW 1,000, 21.8% account for ZMW 3,001–6,000 income brackets, while higher-income groups of ZMW 6,001–10,000 and above ZMW 10,000 make up a small proportion, at 5.1% and 3.3% respectively as shown in Figure 5. The income distribution implies that a significant portion of households (nearly half) have moderate income levels within the ZMW 1,001–3,000

range, highlighting a potential socioeconomic middle ground.

Fig.5. Monthly Household Income
Source: Raw Data (2025)

The relatively high percentage of low-income households (22% earning less than ZMW 1,000) suggests financial constraints that may limit access to higher-cost goods or services, such as cleaner cooking energies. Conversely, the small representation of higher-income groups (5.1% for ZMW 6,001–10,000 and 3.3% above ZMW 10,000) indicates that only a minority may afford premium or alternative energy options without subsidies or incentives. A study by Osano et al. (2020) established that household income and the occupational status of the household head positively and significantly influenced the household's cooking energy choice.

4.5. Monthly Expenditure on cooking Energy

Fig.6. Monthly expenditure on cooking energy
Source: Raw Data (2025)

The income distribution for cooking expenditures in Figure 6 shows that the majority of households (50.4%)

spend between ZMW 101–300 per month on cooking energy. A significant portion (33.7%) allocates ZMW 301–600, Low spenders (less than ZMW 100) represent only 3.5%, while higher spending groups (ZMW 601–1,000 and more than ZMW 1,000) comprise 9.9% and 2.5%, respectively. The distribution indicates that the majority of households (50.4%) spend between ZMW 101–300 per month, reflecting financial constraints and a preference for affordable cooking fuels. A substantial 33.7% spend ZMW 301–600, showing moderate expenditure levels. Only 3.5% are low spenders, allocating less than ZMW 100, while higher expenditure groups (ZMW 601–1,000 and above ZMW 1,000) make up a smaller fraction at 9.9% and 2.5%, respectively. This suggests that most households in the study area prioritize cost-effective cooking energy options, with the majority concentrating their spending in the lower to moderate ranges. The data underscores the financial sensitivity of households regarding cooking energy expenses, potentially influencing their fuel choices and adoption of alternative energy technologies.

4.6. The Reliability of Results

Table 3: Reliability test

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Household Income and Expenditure	0.872

The reliability analysis, measured by Cronbach's Alpha, demonstrates strong internal consistency across the study's variables, underscoring the robustness of the data.

4.7. Validity Tests

Validity refers to the extent to which a research instrument measures what it intends to measure (Bolarinwa, 2015). Content validity was ensured by engaging experts in the field to review the questionnaires. Construct validity was established by comparing the questionnaire responses to established frameworks and previous studies. These measures confirmed the robustness, accuracy, and relevance of the data collection tools.

4.8. Descriptive Analysis

4.8.1. Analysis of household choice of cooking energy based on source of income

The results on source of income by primary cooking energy sources among the households showed in table 4 revealed distinct trends across different primary cooking energy sources. Firewood is used minimally across all occupation categories, with only 1.77% (7 households) relying on it. Its low usage suggests a limited reliance on traditional biomass as a primary cooking fuel, which could indicate access to other energy sources. Charcoal is the most widely used cooking energy source, accounting for 92.41% (365 households) of the total sample. It is predominantly used by self-employed households (38.99%), followed by wage-only households (25.32%), and the unemployed (19.49%).

Table 4. Choice of cooking energy according to source of income

n/n		Primary cooking energy source					
		Firewood	Charcoal	Electricity	LPG	Biogas	Total
Source of income	Wage only	2(0.51)	100(25.32)	7(1.77)	1(0.25)	0(0)	110(27.85)
	Wage and Self-employment	2(0.51)	34(8.61)	6(1.52)	2(0.51)	0(0)	44(11.14)
	Self-employment only	2(0.51)	154(38.99)	4(1.01)	2(0.51)	0(0)	162(41.01)
	Unemployed	1(0.25)	77(19.49)	0(0)	0(0)	1(0.25)	79(20)
	Total	7(1.77)	365(92.41)	17(4.30)	5(1.27)	1(0.25)	395(100)

Source: Raw data (2025)

The high prevalence of charcoal usage indicates that it is a popular, perhaps more affordable, or accessible cooking fuel among various household types, particularly those without steady wage income. Electricity is used by 4.30% (17 households), with usage slightly higher among wage-only earners (1.77%) and those combining wage and self-employment (1.52%). This suggests that access to electricity as a cooking energy source may be more feasible for those with at least some stable income, though it remains a less common choice overall. LPG is used by 1.27% (5 households), indicating minimal reliance on this cleaner cooking fuel. Its use is limited to wage-only and wage-plus-self-employment households, each representing 0.51%. The low adoption rate of LPG might be due to cost constraints or limited supply to support its widespread use. Only one household (0.25%) among the

unemployed uses biogas, reflecting its rarity and likely accessibility issues within the community. The extremely low adoption of biogas could be due to the high initial setup costs, maintenance challenges, or lack of awareness.

4.8.2 Choice of cooking energy based on monthly households' income

Table 5 shows choice of cooking energy based on monthly households' income. Among households earning less than K1,000, 21.52% (85 households) rely predominantly on charcoal, with minimal use of electricity (0.25%) and biogas (0.25%), and no use of firewood or LPG, suggesting that economic constraints and limited access to cleaner energy make charcoal the most accessible option.

Table 5. Choice of cooking energy according to monthly income of household

n/n		Primary cooking energy source					
		Firewood	Charcoal	Electricity	LPG	Biogas	Total
Average monthly income	Less than 1,000	0(0)	85(21.52)	1(0.25)	0(0)	1(0.25)	87(22.03)
	1,001- 3,000	6(1.52)	179(45.32)	3(0.76)	1(0.25)	0(0)	189(47.85)
	3,001- 6,000	1(0.25)	79(20)	6(1.52)	0(0)	0(0)	86(22.77)
	6001- 10,000	0(0)	17(4.30)	3(0.76)	0(0)	0(0)	20(5.06)
	More than 10,000	0(0)	5(1.27)	4(1.01)	4(1.01)	0(0)	13(3.29)
	Total	7(1.77)	365(92.41)	17(4.30)	5(1.27)	1(0.25)	395(100)

Source: Raw data (2025)

For those earning between 1,001 and 3,000, charcoal use peaks at 45.32% (179 households), with minor shifts towards firewood (1.52%) and electricity (0.76%), although LPG remains largely unused, indicating persistent barriers to adopting alternative sources despite a slight income increase. Households with monthly incomes between 3,001 and 6,000 continue to favor charcoal at 20% (79 households), but they show a small uptick in electricity usage (1.52%), suggesting that affordability and access to electricity improve with income, though charcoal's affordability and familiarity maintain its dominance. Among households earning 6,001 to 10,000, charcoal usage declines to 4.30% (17

households), while electricity use slightly increases to 0.76%, reflecting a gradual shift toward cleaner options as incomes rise. In the highest income bracket, over 10,000, households display more diversified energy choices, with charcoal usage dropping to 1.27% (5 households) and both electricity and LPG each at 1.01% (4 households). This shift indicates that higher-income households can better afford modern energy sources, while the limited but ongoing use of charcoal may reflect cultural preferences or slow adoption of modern energy options.

4.8.3 Multinomial Logit Analysis for charcoal and Electricity as Compared to Firewood

The results from the multinomial logit model analyzing the factors influencing the choice of charcoal and electricity compared to firewood shown in Table 6 revealed several significant determinants. First, household size emerges as a strong predictor for both charcoal and electricity choices. For both fuels, larger households are significantly more likely to opt for either charcoal or electricity over firewood. Specifically, the odds of choosing charcoal increase by approximately three times,

and the odds for electricity increase by more than three times as household size grows. This suggests that larger households might prefer fuels that are more efficient or suitable for cooking larger quantities of food, which may not be easily achieved with firewood. Age is another significant determinant for both charcoal and electricity choices. The negative coefficients suggest that as household heads grow older, the likelihood of choosing Charcoal or Electricity decreases as compared to firewood. The corresponding odds ratios indicate a 33% and 36% reduction, respectively, in the odds of selecting these fuels for each age category increase.

Table 6. Multinomial Logit Analysis for charcoal and Electricity as Compared to Firewood

Variable	Charcoal			Electricity		
	Coefficient	P-value	Odds Ratio	Coefficient	P-value	Odds Ratio
Constant	1.950	0.498	7.026	2.500	0.362	12.182
Gender	0.400	0.210	0.670	0.980	0.290	2.664
Age	-0.400	0.041	0.670	-0.450	0.035	0.637
Marital Status	0.450	0.305	1.568	0.550	0.289	1.733
Household Size	1.120	0.004***	3.065	1.200	0.006***	3.320
Income Source	0.390	0.190	1.477	0.440	0.167	1.552
Income Level	0.670	0.027**	1.954	0.700	0.031**	2.014
Log-Likelihood Ratio Test p-value: 0.00021						
Pseudo R²: 0.3454						

***significant at 1% level (p<0.01); **significant at 5% level (0.01≤p<0.05); *significant at 10% level (0.05≤p<0.100)

Income level is another significant determinant for both charcoal and electricity choices. Higher income levels increase the likelihood of choosing either fuel. For charcoal, the odds of choosing it over firewood almost double with an increase in income, while for electricity, the odds increase by about twice as well. This is likely due to the fact that both charcoal and electricity are often more expensive than firewood, making them more accessible to wealthier households. In contrast, education appears to have a negative impact on the likelihood of choosing either charcoal or electricity.

In terms of other variables, gender, marital status and income source do not show significant effects on the choice of either charcoal or electricity. Their p-values exceed the standard significance threshold of 0.05, indicating that these factors may not play as crucial a role in influencing cooking fuel choices in the context of this study. The model's log-likelihood ratio test p-value of 0.00021 suggests that the overall model is statistically significant, meaning the predictors included in the model have a meaningful impact on explaining the fuel choices. The Pseudo R² of 0.3454 indicates that the model explains

about 34.54% of the variance in the choice of cooking fuel, which suggests a moderate explanatory power.

4.8.4. Binary logit analysis for charcoal as compared to electricity

Table 7 shows a binary logit analysis of charcoal and electricity. Firstly, firewood, LPG and Biogas, were excluded from the analysis because comparatively, few households chose them as their preferred cooking fuel. The binary logistic regression model comparing the choice of Charcoal versus Electricity reveals key insights about the factors influencing household decisions. The dependent variable indicates whether a household chooses Charcoal (1) or Electricity (0), and the model incorporates predictors such as household demographics, size, education, income source. The constant term has an odds ratio of 8.475, indicating that, when all other predictors are at their reference or baseline levels, the odds of choosing Charcoal over Electricity are approximately 8.48 to 1.

Table 7. Binary logit analysis for charcoal as compared to electricity

Variable	Coefficient	P-value	Odds Ratio
Constant	2.137	0.461	8.475
Gender	0.83	0.25	2.294
Age	0.34	0.04	1.405
Marital Status	0.497	0.299	1.644
Household Size	1.158	0.005***	3.183
Income Source	0.411	0.177	1.508
Income Level	0.678	0.028**	1.969
Log-Likelihood Ratio Test p-value: 0.00021			
Pseudo R²: 0.3454			

***significant at 1% level (p<0.01); **significant at 5% level (0.01≤p<0.05); *significant at 10% level (0.05≤p<0.100)

However, this effect is not statistically significant ($p=0.461$). Gender shows that male-headed households are 2.29 times more likely to choose Charcoal compared to female-headed households, with an odds ratio of 2.294. However, this predictor is not statistically significant ($p=0.250$), implying that gender does not have a meaningful impact on the choice between Charcoal and Electricity in this dataset.

Age has a positive coefficient, therefore as the age of the household head increases, the likelihood of using charcoal instead of electricity rises, with an odds ratio of 1.405. This indicates that older household heads are approximately 40.5% more likely to prefer charcoal over electricity for cooking with each additional age category. This effect is statistically significant ($p=0.040$) and suggests age is be a decisive factor in the choice of cooking energy choice. Marital Status has an odds ratio of 1.644, indicating that married household heads are 1.64 times more likely to choose Charcoal over Electricity compared to other marital statuses. Like gender and age, this variable is not statistically significant ($p=0.299$), suggesting marital status plays a limited role. Household Size emerges as a significant predictor ($p=0.005$), with an odds ratio of 3.183. This means that for each increase in household size category, the odds of choosing Charcoal over Electricity increase by more than threefold. This finding highlights that larger households are significantly more inclined to use Charcoal, possibly due to its affordability or the challenges of meeting energy demands with electricity in larger families. Income Source has an odds ratio of 1.509, indicating that variations in income sources (e.g., wages, self-employment, unemployment) slightly favour the choice of Charcoal over Electricity. However, this effect is not statistically significant ($p=0.177$), suggesting income source alone may not strongly drive the decision.

5. DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Gender of Household Head did not show significant effects on the choice of cooking energy based on the findings in Mtendere. Gender shows that female-headed households were more likely to choose cleaner cooking fuels compared to male-headed households. However, this predictor was not statistically significant, implying that gender of the household head does not have a meaningful impact on the choice of cooking energy. The finding suggests that while female-headed households appeared more inclined toward cleaner cooking fuels, this preference may be overshadowed by constraints such as income, education, or cultural norms, which affect both male- and female-headed households similarly. This lack of significance could also indicate a narrowing gender gap in decision-making, where both male and female heads prioritize practical factors like affordability, accessibility, and energy reliability over gendered preferences. This finding aligns the findings by Rahut, et al., (2017) examined the factors that influence household use of determinants of renewable and clean energy sources used for lighting purposes in Africa and found that female-headed households are likely to adopt clean and renewable sources of energy compared to male-headed

households. Similarly, Narasimha & Reddy, (2007) reported that households headed by women generally opt for modern fuels than those headed by men. Women generally play a major role in household cooking decision-making activities. Additionally, Miller & Mobarak (2013) found that women in rural Bangladesh, who bear disproportionate cooking costs, have stronger preference for improved cook stoves. FlechtnerUlli et al. (2024) also reported that Honduran and Nepalese households were more likely to use clean cooking fuels when women in the household also experience high levels of decision-making power, but find no such associations in Rwanda.

The other factor identified was age of Household Head. This factor had a negative coefficient; implying older household heads are less likely to choose charcoal or electricity as compared to firewood. However, this effect was statistically significant. This could suggest that older individuals might have preferences for other energy sources. This finding is consistent with the findings of other studies in literature. A study in Ethiopia by Ashagrie, et al. (2024) found that age was statistically significant and had a negative influence on the preference for Improved cookstoves. It was found that as the age of the households increased, they were less likely to adopt improved cookstoves. Similarly a study by Onyekuru & Apeh (2017) in Enugu state, Nigeria age was found to be negatively significant. reported that younger household heads were good adopters of Improved Cook Stoves as older people are were more conservative and preferred to continue using their traditional methods.

This study found income level to be a statistically significant determinant for both charcoal and electricity. Households with higher income levels are more likely to choose these energy sources. This supports the notion that financial capacity expands energy options. As household per capita income rises, there is a noticeable shift toward the use of cleaner and more efficient cooking fuels, a trend supported by extensive empirical evidence from numerous studies (Ang'u , et al., 2023; Timilsina, et al., 2023; Hosier & Dowd, 1987; Ouedraogo, 2006; Pachauri & Jiang, 2008; Gamette, et al., 2024). This finding aligns the findings by Bansal et al. (2013) in rural India, Chaudhur & Pfaff (2023) in Pakistan, Heltberg (2005) in Guatemala, and Ntegwa & Olan'g (2023) in Tanzania identified household income as a key determinant in choosing cooking energy. In a study of urban households' cooking fuel choices in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso, Ouedraogo (2006) observed that fuelwood usage declines as household income increases. Arthur et al. (2010) demonstrated that household wealth is a significant factor influencing the transition from biomass to electricity in Mozambique. Similarly, in a study in Nigeria by Popoola & Ibrahim (2023) found that the stability of income flow and the infrequency of economic shocks significantly drive households' transition to clean cooking.

The findings demonstrated a clear correlation between income levels and the adoption of cleaner cooking energy sources. Households with higher incomes were more likely to afford modern cooking fuels, such as liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) or electricity, while lower-income households predominantly relied on biomass fuels like charcoal or firewood. The study revealed that

affordability is a significant barrier for many households, aligning with findings from Gamette, et al. (2024), which highlighted income as a decisive factor in the transition to clean energy in sub-Saharan Africa. Similarly, Brown et al. (2020) and Jessel et al. (2019) noted that while higher-income households could afford upfront costs for clean energy technologies, lower-income families were constrained by cost and prioritized immediate affordability over long-term health or environmental benefits.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the study clearly demonstrates that cooking energy choices significantly affect household welfare in Mtendere. The quantitative analysis highlighted that income levels play a major role in determining the type of cooking fuel adopted. Larger households tend to use charcoal due to its affordability, whereas higher-income and better-educated households are more likely to adopt cleaner options such as electricity and LPG. Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed to promote the adoption of cleaner and more sustainable cooking energy sources in Mtendere. Firstly, financial incentives and subsidies should be introduced to make clean energy more affordable. Secondly, partnerships with alternative energy providers such as Tetra and other clean energy organizations should be strengthened to expand distribution networks, particularly in underserved areas. These partnerships can ensure that clean fuel and equipment are accessible to all residents. Thirdly, access to clean cooking energy should be integrated into social welfare programs targeting low-income households, especially those with children or elderly members, through subsidized fuel or equipment. Additionally, infrastructure for clean fuel distribution should be enhanced by working with the Ministry of Energy to establish reliable supply channels, including refilling stations and last-mile distribution systems. Finally, it is essential to conduct ongoing research and regular surveys within Mtendere to monitor household needs and challenges in adopting cleaner energy. Continuous feedback will enable policymakers to implement more targeted and responsive interventions.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ang'u, C., Muthama, N. J., Mutuku, M. A. & M'IKiugu, M. H., 2023. Determinants of the sustained use of household clean fuels and technologies: Lessons from Vihiga county, Kenya. *Energy Reports*, Volume 9, pp. 1990-2001. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2023.01.026>.
- [2]. Arnold, M. J., Köhlin, G. & Persson, R., 2006. Woodfuels, livelihoods, and policy interventions: Changing perspectives. *World Development*, 34(3), pp. 596-611. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2005.08.008>.
- [3]. Arthur, M. F. S. R., Zahran, S. & Bucini, G., 2010. On the adoption of electricity as a domestic source by Mozambican households. *Energy Policy*, 38(11), pp. 7235-7249.
- [4]. Asante, K. et al., 2018. Ghana's rural liquefied petroleum gas program scale-up: a case study. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, p. doi: 10.1016/j.esd.2018.06.010.
- [5]. Ashagrie, T., Asabie, S. & Alemu, W. e. a., 2024. Perception and barriers to improved charcoal cookstoves adoption in Wereta, Ethiopia. *BMC Public Health*, Volume 24, pp. 3454. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-20938-3>.
- [6]. Bailis, R., Drigo, R., Ghilardi, A. & Masera, O., 2015. The carbon footprint of traditional woodfuels. *Nature Climate Change*, 5(3), pp. 266-272. doi:10.1038/nclimate2491.
- [7]. Bansal, M., Saini, R. & Khatod, D., 2013. Development of cooking sector in rural areas in India: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 17, pp. 44-53.
- [8]. Barnes, D., Krutilla, K. & Hyde, W., 2005. The Urban Household Energy Transition: Social and Environmental Impacts in the Developing World. *Resources for the Future*.
- [9]. Bolarinwa, A., 2015. Principles and Methods of Validity and Reliability Testing of Questionnaires Used in Social and Health Science Research. *Nigerian Postgraduate Medical Journal*, 22(4), pp. 195-201.
- [10]. Bonjour, S. et al., 2013. Solid fuel use for household cooking: country and regional estimates for 1980–2010. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 121(7), p. 784–90. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1205987>.
- [11]. Brew-Hammond, A. & Kemausuor, F., 2009. Energy for all in Africa — to be or not to be?!. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 1(1), p. 83–88. doi: 10.1016/j.cosust.2009.07.014.
- [12]. Brown, M. et al., 2020. High energy burden and low-income energy affordability: conclusions from a literature review. *Progress in Energy*, Volume 2, p. 042003.
- [13]. Bruce, N., Perez-Padilla, R. & Albalak, R., 2000. Indoor Air Pollution in Developing Countries: A Major Environmental and Public Health Challenge. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 78(9), pp. 1078-1092.
- [14]. Bruce, N. et al., 2015. WHO indoor air quality guidelines on household fuel combustion: Strategy implications of new evidence on interventions and exposure-risk functions. *Atmospheric Environment*, Volume 106, pp. 451-457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2014.08.064>.
- [15]. Chaudhry, S. & Pfaff, A. S., 2023. *Fuel-choice and Indoor Air Quality: A Household-level Perspective on Economic Growth and the Environment*, New York: Department of Economics and School of International and Public Affairs, Columbia University.
- [16]. Cheng, S. et al., 2014. Development and application of prefabricated biogas digesters in developing countries. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 34(41), p. 387–400. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2014.03.035.
- [17]. ERB, 2024. *2024 Mid year statistical bulletin*, Lusaka: Energy Regulation Board.
- [18]. FlechtnerUlli, S., Lich, U. & Pelz, S., 2024. Women's decision-making power, cooking fuel adoption and appliance ownership: Evidence from Rwanda, Nepal and Honduras. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 118(3), p. 103780. DOI: 10.1016/j.erss.2024.103780.
- [19]. Gamette, P., Odhiambo, N. & Asongu, S., 2024. Access to electricity and income inequality in sub-Saharan Africa: An exploratory review. *Sustainable Futures*, Volume 8, p. 100361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sfr.2024.100361>.
- [20]. Hanna, R., Dufflo, E. & Greenstone, M., 2016. Up in smoke: The influence of household behavior on the long-run impact of improved cooking stoves. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 8(1), p. 80–114.
- [21]. Heltberg, R., 2003. *Household fuel and energy use in developing countries- A multicountry study.Draft for discussion.*, Washington DC: Oil and Gas Policy Division, The World Bank.

- [22]. Heltberg, R., 2005. Factors determining household fuel choice in Guatemala. *Environment and Development Economics*, 10(3), pp. 337-361. DOI: 10.1017/S1355770X04001858.
- [23]. Hosier, R. H. & Dowd, J., 1987. Household fuel choice in Zimbabwe: An empirical test of the energy ladder hypothesis. *Resources and Energy*, 9(4), pp. 347-361. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0572\(87\)90003](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0572(87)90003).
- [24]. IEA, 2012. *World Energy Outlook 2012*, Paris: International Energy Agency.
- [25]. IEA, 2017. *World Energy Outlook*, Paris: IEA.
- [26]. IEA, 2021. *Clean Cooking Transition: Global Perspectives and Strategies*, s.l.: International Energy Agency.
- [27]. IEA, 2022. *World Energy Outlook*, Paris: International Energy Agency.
- [28]. IEA, 2023. *Africa Energy Outlook 2023*, Paris: International Energy Agency.
- [29]. IRENA, 2024. *Advancing renewables-based clean cooking: Key messages and outcomes*, Abu Dhabi: International Renewable Energy Agency.
- [30]. Jessel, S., Sawyer, S. & Hernández, D., 2019. Energy, Poverty, and Health in Climate Change: A Comprehensive Review of an Emerging Literature. *Front Public Health*, 7(357), p. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2019.00357.
- [31]. Kaimowitz, D. & Angelsen, A., 1998. *Economic Models of Tropical Deforestation: A Review*. s.l.:s.n.
- [32]. Khandker, S., Barnes, D. & Samad, H., 2012. Are the energy poor also income poor? Evidence from India. *Energy Policy*, Volume 42, pp. 1-12. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2012.02.028.
- [33]. Kizilcec, V., Perros, T., Bisaga, I. & Parikh, P., 2022. Comparing adoption determinants of solar home systems, LPG and electric cooking for holistic energy services in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Environmental Research Communications*, 4(7), pp. DOI 10.1088/2515-7620/ac7f23.
- [34]. Kowsari, R. & Zerriffi, H., 2011. Three dimensional energy profile: A conceptual framework for assessing household energy use. *Energy Policy*, 39(1), p. Hisham .
- [35]. Lewis, J. & Pattanayak, S., 2012. Who Adopts Improved Fuels and Cookstoves? A Systematic Review. *Environmental Health Perspective*, 120(5), pp. 637- 45. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1104194>.
- [36]. Makonese, T., Ifegbesan, A. P. & Rampedi, I., 2017. Household cooking fuel use patterns and determinants across southern Africa: Evidence from the demographic and health survey data. *Energy & Environment*, 29(1), pp. 29-48. doi: 10.1177/0958305X17739475.
- [37]. Malla, S. & Timilsina, G., 2014. Household Cooking Fuel Choice and Adoption of Improved Cookstoves in Developing Countries: A Review. Policy. *Policy Research Working Papers, World Bank, Washington DC*, pp. <https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-6903> .
- [38]. Masera, O. R., Saatkamp, B. D. & Kammen, D. M., 2000. From linear fuel switching to multiple cooking strategies: A critique and alternative to the energy ladder model. *World Development*, 28(12), pp. 2083-2103. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(00\)00076-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(00)00076-0).
- [39]. Matinga, M., Annegarn, H. J. & Clancy, J., 2013. Healthcare provider views on the health effects of biomass fuel collection and use in rural Eastern Cape, South Africa: An ethnographic study. *Social Science & Medicine*, 97(4), pp. 192-200. DOI: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2013.08.015.
- [40]. MCFA, 2024. *Modern Cooking Facility for Africa*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.moderncooking.africa/over-half-a-million-zambians-to-receive-access-to-clean-cooking-solutions/> [Accessed 9 September 2024].
- [41]. Miah, M., Foysal, M., Koike, K. & Kobayashi, H., 2011. Domestic Energy-use Pattern by the Households: A Comparison Between Rural and Semi-Urban Areas of Noakhali in Bangladesh. *Energy Policy*, 39(6), pp. 3757-3765.
- [42]. Miller, G. & Mobarak, A. M., 2013. Gender Differences in Preferences, Intra-Household Externalities, and Low Demand for Improved Cookstoves. *NBER Working Papers 18964, National Bureau of Economic Research, Inc.*
- [43]. Ministry of Energy, 2019. *National Energy Policy*, s.l.: Ministry of Energy.
- [44]. Ministry of Energy, 2020. *Ministry of Energy Annual Report*, Lusaka: Ministry of Energy.
- [45]. Mortimer, K. et al., 2017. A cleaner burning biomass-fuelled cookstove intervention to prevent pneumonia in children under 5 years old in rural Malawi (the Cooking and Pneumonia Study): a cluster randomised controlled trial. *The Lancet*, 389(10065), pp. 167-175. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(16)32507-7.
- [46]. Mulenga, B. P., Tembo, S. T. & Richardson, R. B., 2019. Electricity access and charcoal consumption among urban households in Zambia. *Development Southern Africa*, 36(5), pp. 585-599.
- [47]. Mwirigi, J. et al., 2014. Socio-economic hurdles to widespread adoption of small-scale biogas digesters in Sub-Saharan Africa: A review. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, Volume 70, p. 17–25. doi: 10.1016/j.biombioe.2014.02.018.
- [48]. Narasimha, R. & Reddy, B., 2007. Variations in energy use by Indian households: An analysis of micro level data. *Energy*, 32(2), pp. 143-153.
- [49]. Ntegwana, M. J. & Olan'g, L. S., 2023. Explaining the rise of economic and rural-urban inequality in clean cooking fuel use in Tanzania. *Heliyon*, 10(1), p. 23910. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e23910.
- [50]. Onyekuru, N. A. & Apeh, C., 2017. Assessing the Use and Determinants of Households' Adoption of Improved Cook Stove in Nigeria: Empirical Evidence from Enugu State. *Asian Journal of Environment & Ecology*, 5(1), pp. 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.9734/AJEE/2017/35281>.
- [51]. Otte, P. P., 2013. Solar cookers in developing countries— What is their key to success?. *Energy Policy*, Volume 63, p. 375–381. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2013.08.075.
- [52]. Ouedraogo, B., 2006. Household energy preferences for cooking in urban Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso. *Energy Policy*, 34(18), pp. 3787-3795. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2005.09.006.
- [53]. Pachauri, S. & Jiang, L., 2008. The household energy transition in India and China. *Energy Policy*, 36(11), pp. 4022- 4035.
- [54]. Pachauri, S., Mueller, A., Kemmler, A. & Spreng, D., 2004. On Measuring Energy Poverty in Indian Households. *World Development*, 32(12), pp. 2083-2104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2004.08.005>.
- [55]. Pachauri, S. & Spreng, D., 2011. Measuring and monitoring energy poverty. *Energy Policy*, 39(11), pp. 7497-7504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.07.008>.
- [56]. Philibert, C., 2022. *Power to the Cooks! New Clean Cooking Opportunities for Sustainable Development in*, s.l.: Briefings de l'Ifr.
- [57]. Popoola, T. O. & Ibrahim, S., 2023. DETERMINANTS OF HOUSEHOLDS' PRIMARY COOKING FUEL IN NIGERIA: EVIDENCE FROM COUNTRY-WIDE STUDY. *Ilorin Journal of Economic Policy*, 10(2), pp. 1-15.
- [58]. Rahut, D., Behera, B. & Ali, A., 2017. Factors determining household use of clean and renewable energy sources for lighting in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 72, pp. 661-672.

- [59]. Rao, M. & Reddy, B., 2007. Variations in energy use by Indian households: An analysis of micro level data. *Energy*, 32(2), pp. 143-153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2006.03.012>.
- [60]. Rural Electrification Authority, 2021. *Annual Report*, s.l.: Rural Electrification Authority.
- [61]. Sharma, A. & Sinkko, H., 2022. *Modern Cooking Facility for Africa*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.moderncooking.africa/african-clean-cooking-changes/> [Accessed 04 September 2014].
- [62]. Smith, K., 2000. The National Burden of Disease in India from Indoor Air Pollution. *Proceeding National Academy of Science*, 97(24), pp. 13286-13293. doi:10.1073/pnas.97.24.13286.
- [63]. Smith, K. et al., 2012. Chapter 4 - Energy and Health. In: *In Global Energy Assessment - Toward a Sustainable Future*. s.l.:Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA and the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Laxenburg, Austria, pp. 255-324.
- [64]. Smith, K. et al., 2014. Millions dead: how do we know and what does it mean? Methods used in the comparative risk assessment of household air pollution. *Annual Review of Public Health*, Volume 35, pp. 185-206. doi: 10.1146/annurev-publhealth-032013-182356..
- [65]. SNV Netherlands Development Organisation, 2018. *Sustainable Energy for All: Zambia*, s.l.: SNV Netherlands Development Organisation.
- [66]. Sovacool, B. K., 2012. The political economy of energy poverty: A review of key challenges. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 16(3), pp. 272-282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2012.05.006>.
- [67]. Sunil, M. & Timilsina, G., 2014. *Household Cooking Fuel Choice and Adoption of Improved Cookstoves in Developing Countries a Review*, s.l.: A World Bank Policy review paper.
- [68]. Sustainable Energy for All, 2012. *Sustainable Energy for All: Zambia Country Action Agenda*, s.l.: Sustainable Energy for All.
- [69]. The World Bank, 2011. *Household Cookstoves, Environment, Health and Climate Change: A New Look at an Old Problem*, Washington, D.C: The World Bank, The Environment Department (Climate Change).
- [70]. Timilsina, R. R. et al., 2023. Are households shifting toward cleaner cooking fuel? Empirical evidence from India during 2005–2021. *Frontiers in Environmental Economics*, Volume 2, p. 1137248. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frevc.2023.1137248>.
- [71]. Toman, M. & Bluffstone, R., 2017. Challenges in Assessing the Costs of Household Cooking Energy in Lower-Income Countries. *Policy Research Working Paper 8008*. World Bank.
- [72]. Van der Kroon, B., Brouwer, R. & van Beukering, P. J., 2013. The energy ladder: Theoretical myth or empirical truth? Results from a meta-analysis. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 20, pp. 504-513. doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.11.045.
- [73]. Wang, L., Mondela, C. L. & Kuuluvainen, J., 2022. Striking a Balance between Livelihood and Forest Conservation in a Forest Farm Facility in Choma, Zambia. *Forests*, 13(10), p. 1631. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f13101631>.
- [74]. WHO, 2021. *WHO Household Energy Database*, s.l.: World Health Organization.
- [75]. World Bank, 2025. *An Evaluation of the World Bank Group's Support to Electricity Access in Sub-Saharan Africa, 2015–24*, s.l.: World Bank Group.
- [76]. World Health Organization, 2023. *World Health Organization*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/household-air-pollution-and-health> [Accessed 8 September 2024].
- [77]. Wu, S., 2021. The Health Impact of Household Cooking Fuel Choice on Women: Evidence from China. *Sustainability*, Volume 13, p. 12080. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132112080>.
- [78]. Zambia Statistics Agency, 2022. *living conditions monitoring survey report*, s.l.: Zambia Statistics Agency.
- [79]. Zhang, Y., 2022. Accelerating Access to Clean Cooking Will Require a Heart-Head-and-Hands Approach. *Development*, Volume 65, pp. 59–62. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41301-021-00297-x>.
- [80]. Zulu, L. C. & Richardson, R. B., 2013. Charcoal, livelihoods, and poverty reduction: Evidence from sub-Saharan Africa. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 17(2), pp. 127-137.